

DISBOND MONITORING OF ADHESIVE JOINTS REINFORCED WITH CARBON NANOFIBRES

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the ability of carbon nanofibre (CNF) networks for *in situ* monitoring of fatigue induced disbond damage in carbon fibre adhesive bonded joints. The mode I fatigue delamination behaviour of composite joints bonded with an unmodified epoxy adhesive and 0.7 wt% CNF modified epoxy adhesive are evaluated. The inclusion of CNFs in the epoxy adhesive increases its conductivity by five orders of magnitude while simultaneously retarding the delamination growth rate. The mode I critical strain energy of the CNF modified adhesive increases by about five folds from 88 J/m² to 450 J/m² under cyclic fatigue loading. The improved electrical conductivity is utilized to evaluate the ability of the CNF network to monitor and detect the fatigue induced disbond damage by *in situ* measuring the resistance changes using a four probe setup. The changes in total resistance was a function of the bulk electrical resistivity of the adhesive and the bond dimensions, which were related to the disbond length to model and determine the size of the disbond. Good agreement were found between the optical disbond observations and the calculated disbond length using the *in situ* resistance measurements, therefore proving the ability of CNFs to not only detect delamination as small as 1 mm in composite bonded joints but also retard its growth rate.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the key challenges for increasing the uptake of fibre composites is the need for joining during initial modular construction. Adhesive bonded joining provides many advantages such as high strength to weight ratio, low stress concentration, fewer processing requirements and good

environmental resistance[1]. However, a major drawback with adhesive joints is their inability to be disassembled for periodic inspection. Therefore, bolted joints are currently preferred in the industry for joining composite parts, in spite of their low bearing strength and the resultant higher stress concentration regions emanating from the discontinuity of the reinforcing fibres[2].

Thermosetting epoxy polymers are widely used for bonding purposes due to their superior mechanical property and good resistance to environmental degradation. However, due to their inherently brittle structure, they offer poor resistance to delamination or disbond damage[3]. An undetected barely visible damage in epoxy bonded joints can rapidly grow to failure under cyclic loads due to the low fatigue strain energy threshold of epoxy polymers[4,5]. Since regular visual aircraft inspection carried out during service are limited to the detection of flaws that lie near the surface, an underlying disbond could remain undetected between service intervals and therefore has mandated overdesigning of the composite structures[6]. Moreover, current damage inspection techniques are limited to ultrasonic, radiography and acoustic emission for adhesively bonded composite joints. Potential drop and eddy current technique cannot be used due to the absence of through-thickness conductivity in bonded composite joints as a result of the dielectric property of the epoxy matrix and adhesives[7]. With regular visual inspections limited to the detection of flaws that lie near the surface, there is a strong need for additional repeatable and reliable non-destructive inspection techniques that could be applied on field and *in situ* to monitor the integrity of bonded composite joints. In addition, a lightweight bonded joint design is only possible if the damage growth behaviour is sufficiently slow to enable the planning of an inspection schedule that enable reliable detection of damage before it becomes critical[8].

Recent studies have shown that conductive carbon nanofillers such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs)[9,10] or carbon nanofibres (CNFs)[11,12] can form conductive networks in polymeric materials at extremely low weight fractions while simultaneously improving the fracture toughness. These conductive fillers have been incorporated into fibre composites for damage detection[13–16]. More recently, Lim et al.[17] reported the use of CNT networks to monitor the initiation of damage in epoxy bonded lap joints under quasi-static and dynamic tensile loading. Similarly, Mactabi et al.[18] studied the electromechanical response of CNT networks incorporated in bonded lap joints under tensile fatigue loading. In adhesives containing conductive carbon nanofillers, any damage to the nanofiller network due to crack growth would result in a permanent electrical response which could be used to determine the size of the disbond or delamination damage. The potential application of this technique to monitor and detect mode I fatigue crack growth in epoxy bonded composite joints has never been investigated.

The present study focuses on utilizing CNFs in epoxy adhesive bonded composite joints to *in situ* monitor disbond damage while simultaneously improving the resistance to crack growth under mode I fatigue. The mode I fatigue crack growth resistance of the CNF modified epoxy adhesive bonded composite joints is compared to the neat epoxy adhesive. The electrical response of the nanocomposite adhesive is measured in-situ during mode I fatigue test using DC potential drop technique. The in-situ resistance measurements are used to determine the size of the propagating crack.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy adhesive used for bonding composites was blend of five parts of bisphenol A '105' and one part of the hardener '206' (from West System). Commercially-available vapour-grown carbon nanofibres, Pyrograf® - III PR-24-HHT and supplied by Applied Sciences Inc., USA, were employed as the nanofiller. Carbon fibre composite substrates were manufactured using 12 plies of unidirectional T700 carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg (VTM 264 supplied by Applied Composites Group). The substrates, with dimensions of 300 mm x 250 mm x 2.5 mm, were cured and consolidated in an autoclave at 120^o C for 1 hr., in accordance with the manufacturer's recommended cure process. The substrate surfaces were abraded using 320 grit aluminium oxide abrasive paper, cleaned under running tap water for about 2 minutes, degreased with acetone, and finally cleaned with distilled water to remove any surface impurities. A three-roll mill (Dermamill 100) was used to disperse the CNFs in the liquid epoxy resin. Firstly, 0.7 wt% of the CNFs were hand mixed with dispersion-aiding additives based upon solvent-free acrylate copolymers, namely Disperbyk-191 and -192 (supplied by BYK ®). The

dispersive surfactants that were added to the CNFs were equal to the weight of the CNFs, resulting in a mixture of CNFs:191:192 weight ratio of 1:1:1. The CNF-surfactant mixture was then added to the epoxy resin, with no curing agent yet added, and hand mixed for 5 minutes. This mixture was then passed four times through the three-roll mill at 150 rpm and the gap size was gradually reduced with each subsequent pass to achieve a homogeneous dispersion of CNFs.

The surface treated carbon fibre composite substrates (150 mm x 250 mm) were placed between glass fibre frames which were used as a dam to prevent the epoxy mixture from flowing out of the joint. Spacers, 2 mm in thickness made of glass slides, were placed at both ends of the joint to control the thickness of the epoxy layer between the substrates. Teflon-coated tape about 30 mm long and 11 μm thick was placed at an approximately equal distance between the two substrates, at one end of the joint, to act as a crack starter. The amine-based curing agent was added to the dispersed CNF/epoxy resin mixture and hand-mixed for approximately 5 minutes. This CNF-modified epoxy resin mixture was then poured between the substrates. The epoxy adhesive was then cured at room temperature (i.e. 250 C) for 48 h in total to form the epoxy nanocomposite. The joints were allowed to cure under ambient conditions prior to cutting into 20 mm wide double-cantilever beam (DCB) adhesively-bonded specimens. Composite bonded joints with two different adhesives are investigated in this study namely, unmodified epoxy adhesive and 0.7 wt% CNF modified adhesive. For the 0.7 wt% CNF sample, the electrical contact were established by sanding the outer surface of the adherends to slightly expose the carbon fibres and strain gauge wires were bonded with conductive silver paint. The contact points were covered with an insulating tape. Non-conductive grips were used to isolate the DCB sample from the load frame. The mode I fatigue delamination test were conducted under displacement control at 5 Hz with a stress intensity ratio of 0.5 by adapting the ASTM D6115-97 standard on a 3 kN electromagnetic pulse driven Instron E3000 fatigue test rig. In situ resistance measurements were acquired by a four probe resistance measurement technique using Delloger80 dataker during mode I fatigue delamination tests. The crack growth increments were recorded using a travelling microscope. The fatigue test setup is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1: Experimental setup for *in situ* resistance monitoring during mode I fatigue test

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Crack growth resistance of the CNF modified adhesive

Fig. 2 shows the delamination growth rate curves for the unmodified and CNF modified adhesive bonded composite joints recorded during mode I fatigue tests performed under displacement control and the stress intensity ratio of 0.5. The addition of 0.7 wt% CNF in the adhesive increased the critical strain energy by about five folds from 88 J/m^2 to 450 J/m^2 . Similarly, the threshold strain energy increased from 19.5 J/m^2 to 55 J/m^2 . This shows that the unmodified adhesive is a low toughness epoxy. However, the addition of just 0.7 wt% CNF increases its fracture toughness by about five folds which results in improved delamination resistance.

Fig. 2: Comparison of the delamination growth rate curves for unmodified and 0.7 wt% CNF modified adhesive bonded composite joints

Fig. 3: (a) Crack propagation in carbon fibre adhesive joint during mode I DCB fatigue testing 0.7 CNF sample; (b) crack bridging and pull-out of CNF in adhesive joint

Fig. 4: SEM micrograph of the fracture surface 0.7 wt% CNF modified adhesive; (a) CNF pull-out, debonding and rupture; (b) epoxy void growth around CNF

As shown in **Fig. 3**, the crack growth was cohesive through the adhesive, with almost equal amounts of adhesive on both the fractured surfaces. The improvement in the delamination resistance of the CNF modified adhesive was due to the additional toughening from the presence of the CNFs. As can be seen from **Fig. 4a**, SEM micrographs of the fracture surface revealed a large number of CNFs pulled out of the adhesive. In addition, a significant number of large voids are present around CNFs which are debonded from the epoxy (**Fig. 4b**). These voids are indicative of the plastic void growth of epoxy in the process zone. The aggregate increase in the critical strain energy is a combination of the energy dissipated by (a) interfacial debonding of the CNFs from the epoxy, (b) the frictional energy associated with the CNFs now pulling-out from the epoxy, (c) void growth of the epoxy which initiates from the hole created by the debonded CNFs, and (d) the CNFs then bridging and finally rupturing across the crack faces, behind the advancing crack tip (**Fig. 3b**). The CNF pull-out mechanism is typically the most dominant mechanism in increasing the fracture energy which results in improved delamination resistance of the adhesive joints.

3.2 *In situ* resistance response during mode I fatigue crack growth

The addition of just 0.7 wt% CNF to the epoxy adhesive increases its conductivity by five order of magnitude to 10^{-4} S/m. The increased conductivity due to the formation of percolating network of CNF was utilized to monitor the change in electrical response to disbond damage. *In situ* resistance measurements were acquired during the mode I fatigue delamination test. The resistance measurements were recorded for crack growth above the applied fracture energy of 160 J/m^2 up to the critical fracture energy of the CNF modified adhesive. As shown in **Fig. 5a**, the resistance increased monotonically with increasing number of cycles. **Fig 5b** shows the effect of displacement on the transient resistance measurements recorded during cycling. The noise in the resistance signal emanating from the datataker was significantly low in comparison to the total resistance. While the larger undulation in the resistance signal were due to the loading and unloading of the DCB specimen. The difference between the maxima and the minima of these undulations were only 2 percent of the total increase in the resistance. However, the resistance increased at the maximum and decreased at the minimum crack opening displacement, such that there was an irreversible increase in resistance after each cycle. The increase in resistance likely corresponds to the disbond of adhesive, since the joint failure was cohesive in the adhesive. The change in the total resistance is due to the shortening of the un-cracked ligament ahead of the crack. Since the total resistance is a function of the electric resistivity of the adhesive and structure's dimensions (width and length), the disbond length can be explicitly related to the measured resistance,

$$R = \frac{\rho t}{(L-a)b} \quad (1)$$

where ρ , L , t , b , and a denote the electric resistivity of the CNF modified adhesive, the length, thickness and width of the adhesive, and the crack length. Changes in the total resistance ΔR can be expressed in terms of the crack growth Δa ,

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{a/L}{1-a/L} \quad (2)$$

which furnishes a relationship for determining the disbond length in an adhesive bonded joint. The effect of disbond length on the resistance measurements are shown in **Fig 5c**. The change in resistance measured during fatigue test is in good agreement with model based on Eq. (2). The resistance increases with increasing disbond length. The results show that the crack growth modifies the charge conduction pathways within the CNF modified adhesive resulting in a resistance change.

Fig. 5: *In situ* resistance response during mode I cyclic fatigue testing (a) at 5 Hz, (b) at 0.01 Hz fatigue cycling and (c) changes in resistance with increasing disbond length

Fig. 6: Comparison of the optical observations and the calculated disbond length from Eq. (1) using *in situ* resistance measurements

3.3 Disbond detection from *in situ* resistance measurements

Fig. 6 shows the comparison of the optical observation and calculated disbond length based on Eq. (1) using the *in situ* resistance measurements obtained during the mode I fatigue testing. The calculated crack length is in good agreement with the optically observed crack length. Moreover, the resistance monitoring technique is also able to capture the increase in the crack growth rate at higher

applied fracture energy. Therefore in a conductive nanofiller modified adhesive bond joint the changes in resistance could be effectively used for in-situ monitoring of crack growth. The resistance based crack detection technique is uncomplicated and can be applied on field by any maintenance personal between major service intervals or during service to monitor the structural integrity of the bonded composite structures.

4 CONCLUSION

The ability of the carbon nanofibre (CNF) networks for *in situ* monitoring of disbond and delamination damage in carbon fibre adhesive bonded joints under fatigue loading is evaluated. The inclusion of 0.7 wt% CNFs in the epoxy adhesive increases its conductivity by five orders of magnitude to 10^{-4} S/m while simultaneously retarding the delamination growth rate. The mode I critical strain energy of the CNF modified adhesive increases by about five folds from 88 J/m^2 to 450 J/m^2 under mode I cyclic fatigue loading. Similarly, the threshold strain energy increased from 19.5 J/m^2 to 55 J/m^2 . The main toughening mechanisms which led to the increase in the delamination resistance for the CNF toughened adhesive were identified to be (a) interfacial debonding of the CNFs from the epoxy, (b) the frictional energy associated with the CNFs now pulling-out from the epoxy, (c) void growth of the epoxy which initiates from the hole created by the debonded CNFs, and (d) the CNFs bridging and finally rupturing across the crack faces, behind the advancing crack tip. The improved electrical conductivity was utilized to evaluate the ability of the CNF network to monitor and detect the fatigue induced disbond damage by *in situ* measuring the resistance changes using a four probe setup. The changes in total resistance was a function of the bulk electrical resistivity of the adhesive and the bond dimensions, which were related to the disbond length to model and determine the size of the disbond. Good agreement were found between the optical disbond observations and the calculated disbond length using the *in situ* resistance measurements, therefore proving the ability of CNFs to not only detect delamination in composite bonded joints but also retard its growth rate.

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